

IMPACT OF LASER SHOCK PEENING ON FATIGUE STRENGTH OF ADDITIVELY MANUFACTURED ALSI10MG

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This study investigates the fatigue strength of additively manufactured AlSi10Mg under cyclic loading, focusing on the high cycle fatigue domain (HCF). Specimens were produced using Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF), with the main objective of analysing fatigue strength concerning various post-processing surface treatments. The hourglass-shaped specimens were printed in a single batch, and six distinct groups of specimens were tested. Three series were left as-built, while three series were machined to achieve specific dimensions and surface roughness. Two setups of Laser Shock Peening (LSP) were applied for two groups of as-built specimens and two groups of machined specimens. Fatigue testing was conducted using a resonant pulsator. Surface roughness and residual stress depth profiles were analysed. Thermal response on the sample surface was monitored with an infrared thermal camera, enabling fatigue life prediction with fewer samples.

Keywords: Laser Shock Peening, Additive manufacturing, Fatigue Strength, High cycle fatigue

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, additive manufacturing has emerged as a revolutionary technology for fabricating complex and lightweight components across various industries. Among the materials extensively explored in this domain is AlSi10Mg, an aluminium alloy known for its excellent strength-to-weight ratio and favourable mechanical properties. Understanding the fatigue behaviour of additively manufactured AlSi10Mg is of utmost importance, particularly for applications subject to cyclic loading in the high cycle fatigue domain (HCF).

The requirement for intricate and lightweight components has driven the adoption of additive manufacturing (AM) as a cost-effective solution. Industries are progressively exploring novel and complex shapes to attain objectives like weight reduction, enhanced thermal control, and component integration. AM empowers rapid alterations in design without incurring additional expenditures. It expedites product development and shortens time-to-market by streamlining research, development,

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and costs through swift prototyping and effective design iterations, thereby obviating the necessity for expensive tooling.

This study explores the fatigue strength analysis of additively manufactured AlSi10Mg. It focuses on the HCF regime. Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF) technology was employed to produce the specimens, providing precise control over the material's microstructure and mechanical properties. The main objective was to investigate the influence of different post-processing surface treatments on the fatigue strength of the specimens, while focusing on the surface alterations by the Laser Shock Peening (LSP) procedure. LSP is an advanced surface treatment technique that harnesses the power of high-energy pulsed laser beams to create shock waves on the surface layer of materials. This process initiates a remarkable transformation, wherein the shock waves propagate from the surface into the interior of the material. As a consequence, the material experiences significant compressive residual stresses and plastic strains [1].

In addition, to these benefits, AM comes with certain limitations, including issues like suboptimal surface quality characterised by surface roughness and porosity, as well as challenges such as the generation of tensile stresses due to rapid thermal cycling, lower fatigue life, non-uniform material distribution impacting microstructure, and notable dimensional tolerances. Particularly, the AlSi10Mg alloy is susceptible to porosity-related defects, a common concern among aluminium alloys when compared to their weldable steel counterparts. Defects that are less problematic in other aluminium alloys arise due to the alloy's exceptional thermal conductivity and high reflectivity, necessitating higher laser power for a stable melt pool. Moreover, the oxidation of Al alloys results in the entrapment of oxide inclusions, creating vulnerable spots within the material [2].

At present, L-PBF finds application in demanding sectors such as aerospace (in components like rocket combustion chambers and engine parts), medical applications (including joint replacements), and the tooling industry (for die casting tools, forging, and cutting tools) [4; 5; 6].

To enhance both the surface quality (surface roughness and porosity) and surface integrity (residual stresses, microhardness, and microstructure) of parts produced through Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF), various post-processing techniques are employed. These techniques include heat treatment, mechanical and chemical polishing, mechanical shot peening, sand blasting, and laser shock peening. Among these options, laser shock peening (LSP) has gained prominence in treating LPBF products due to its unique ability to simultaneously enhance both surface quality and integrity [3]. LSP effectively tackles material limitations, offering improved thermal management and increased fatigue life, or capitalising on enhanced mechanical properties to mitigate cracking concerns [1].

During LSP, the intense laser pulses generate a localised and rapid heating of the material's surface. This sudden thermal expansion results in a high-pressure plasma formation at the surface, which in turn launches the shock waves into the material core. The interaction between the shock waves and the material induces compressive plastic deformation. The resulting compressive stresses act to counterbalance any tensile stresses that might exist in the material, thus enhancing its resistance to fatigue, stress corrosion, and other forms of mechanical degradation.

The depth and intensity of the compressive residual stresses induced by LSP can be controlled by adjusting various parameters, such as laser energy, pulse duration, and the number of laser shots. Additionally, LSP can induce beneficial changes in the microstructure of the material, improving its mechanical properties, including hardness and fatigue life.

The combination of LPBF, post-processing surface treatments, LSP, and advanced testing techniques provides a comprehensive framework for studying the fatigue behaviour of additively manufactured AlSi10Mg. The results from this study will contribute to improving the understanding of the

material's fatigue performance and optimising its potential applications in critical engineering components subjected to cyclic loading and demanding environments.

To expand the fatigue life prediction and to optimise the testing process, an infrared thermal camera was utilised to monitor the thermal response on the specimen surface, enabling more efficient fatigue life prediction from fewer samples [7; 8; 9]. This analysis not only allows for a comprehensive assessment of LSP's effects but also lays the foundation for fatigue life prediction, as demonstrated in recent publications that share a similar focus [10; 11]. In some cases, e.g., [10], a single sample was used to estimate the lifetime in the HCF region from 1,000 to 1,000,000 cycles with a relatively high success rate. Ideally, this method could be used to estimate the lifetime on a single sample and thus speed up the calibration of, for example, heat treatment additively manufactured specimens.

Thermal analysis and methods derived from it to predict the fatigue life [10] and to estimate fatigue limits [12; 13; 14] can be implemented, leading to a significant reduction in the number of required specimens compared to conventional testing approaches. This advancement holds great promise in enhancing the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of fatigue testing, making it a valuable tool for optimising the performance of materials and components subjected to cyclic loading conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Printing of specimen

This research focuses on investigating the fatigue behaviour of AlSi10Mg aluminium alloy manufactured using LPBF. Hourglass-shaped fatigue specimens with a critical cross-section diameter of 9 mm and a transition fillet radius of 60 mm were used for the fatigue experiments, Fig. 1. The fatigue specimens were equipped with a machined head featuring an M18x1 thread, enabling secure fixation to the Amsler HFP 422 resonant pulsator, equipped with a 100 kN load cell. During testing, the loading was applied exclusively in tension ($R=0.1$).

FIGURE 1 (a) Fatigue test specimen; (b) Both specimens are treated with LSP - the upper one with parameters LSP1 and the lower one with LSP2.

All specimens were printed in the vertical direction within one build cycle by Concept Laser M2 printer. The aluminium alloy is manufactured following a specific machine default setup, employing a layer-by-layer construction with each layer having a height of 25 μm . The initial layers on skin of the specimen are formed using a lower energy input (refer to Table 1) to ensure an optimal surface roughness, a critical factor affecting the fatigue damage process. In the next step, the specimen contour is created further inward using higher energy input, encompassing the inner space up to 2

mm below the specimen surface, maintaining the same layer height of 25 μm . In that moment, the platform moves downward, and new skin and contour layers are manufactured. A high energy input is applied every second layer, strategically melting the powder in the core area in a chess-board pattern to achieve higher productivity in this area.

TABLE 1 Parameters of the AM process.

	Power [W]	Speed [mm/s]	Trace spacing [mm]	Spot size [μm]	Layer height [mm]
Skin	200	800	0.112	140	0.025
Contour	370	1400	0.112	190	0.025
Core	370	1400	0.112	190	0.050

Six groups of specimens were formed, see Table 2. Number of specimens printed on a single platform was not sufficient to cover also the NoLSP(M) group within fatigue experiments. The specimens which had to be machined were produced with larger diameters to reach the identical cross-sectional characteristics after machining, see also Fig. 2.

TABLE 2 Series description using colour coding to distinguish heat treatment of the specimens. (M) ~ machined, (A) ~ as-built

ID-code	Surface treatment	LSP (parameters)	Colour coding	Fatigue tests	Residual stress measurements
NoLSP(A)	Left As-printed (A)	None	Green	X	X
NoLSP(M)	Machined to $R_a = 0.8\mu\text{m}$ (M)	None	Black		X
LSP1(A)	Left As-printed (A)	LSP-1	Blue	X	X
LSP2(A)	Left As-printed (A)	LSP-2	Red	X	X
LSP1(M)	Machined to $R_a = 0.8\mu\text{m}$ (M)	LSP-1	Orange	X	X
LSP2(M)	Machined to $R_a = 0.8\mu\text{m}$ (M)	LSP-2	Purple	X	X

B. Laser Shock Peening

The study involved fatigue testing of five groups of specimens, each comprising 11 specimens. Within these groups, ten specimens were utilised to establish the S-N curve. One specimen was set aside for analysing heat dissipation via S-H (self-heating) tests specific in continuous monitoring of surface temperature across a range of tested amplitudes. Prior to testing, all specimens underwent the artificial aging heat treatment by heating them to 200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 hours in a furnace, followed by air-cooling to ambient temperature. The positions of specimens from individual groups from Table 2 can be found marked in Fig. 2 (b).

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Conventionally during LSP processing, the surface of the part is protected by sacrificial coating (most often black vinyl tape). This coating serves two purposes as it improves energy absorption from the laser pulse into the material and it protects the surface of the treated part from generated high-temperature plasma. In this study no protective coating was used, thus the process cannot be described as strictly cold-working; two different Laser Shock Peening strategies were applied as described in Table 3. We can observe Fig. 1 to illustrate distinctions between LSP parameters, where the upper specimen (LSP1) exhibits a significantly finer surface compared to the lower one (LSP2). These differences arise from the specific LSP parameters employed.

TABLE 3 Values of global evaluation parameters obtained for selected specimens.

ID-code	Pulse energy [J]	Pulse length [ns]	Overlap [-]	Rep. rate [Hz]	Spot size Φ [mm]	Power density [GW/c m2]	Wavelength [nm]
LSP1	0.2	17	50%	10	0.7	3.06	1064
LSP2	1.0	17	50%	10	1.1	6.19	1064

FIGURE 2 (a) Printing platform directly after printing in Concept Laser M2. (b) Platform separated into five different groups of fatigue specimens with colour markings. The movement of the recoater and flow of atmosphere directions are visualised. Samples on the right side of the platform were used for residual stress analysis.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A) Residual stress analysis

The residual stresses as a consequence of LSP were measured using Rigaku Auto Mate II x-ray diffractometer with D/teX Ultra detector using chromium anode. Material was removed electrochemically in steps using Lectro-pol 5 with sulphuric acid-based electrolyte as to not introduce

additional stresses. The stresses were measured in two directions (parallel and perpendicular to sample axis) and the corrective calculation from material relaxation and into the axial and tangent directions was performed as in [15].

The results of axial and tangential residual stresses provided in Fig. 3 clearly demonstrate

the significant effect of LSP on the residual stresses within the specimens. Extensive measurements were conducted, focusing on the depth of 0.9 mm below the surface in most cases, to precisely assess the induced residual stresses. As anticipated, all residual stresses induced by LSP were found to be in compression, which is a desirable outcome as it should enhance the material resistance to fatigue degradation.

Notably, the differences between the LSP1 and LSP2 configurations were particularly pronounced in the initial layers of the as-printed specimens see Fig. 3 a). However, as the measurement depth increased beyond 0.2 mm, the differences between the two configurations became negligible. This observation suggests that the impact of LSP on residual stresses primarily affects the near-surface region, leading to more compressive residual stresses for the LSP1 variant with pulses of lower energy.

FIGURE 3 (a) Residual stresses of AISi10Mg of three configuration of as-built specimens (NoLSP(A), LSP1(A) a LSP2(A)); (b) Residual stresses of AISi10Mg of three configuration of machined specimens (NoLSP(M), LSP1(M) a LSP2(M))

For the machined specimens see Fig. 3 b)., while the differences between LSP1 and LSP2 configurations in the surface characteristics observed in Fig. 1 were still evident, the projection of the LSP setup in the near-surface layer was nearly identical, while higher compressive stresses were characteristic deeper in the core for the LSP2 variant. It is interesting to note that if the axial and tangential residual stresses were relatively similar for each configuration for as-built specimens, higher compressive axial residual stresses were observed compared to the compressive tangential residual stresses for the machined configurations.

If the results of LSP variants are compared with the data from NoLSP variants, it is obvious that LSP simply shifts the original residual stresses to compressive domain, and the difference in the axial and tangential residual stresses for each variant (machined, as-built) is preserved, except of the layer closest to the surface, where the residual stresses after LSP shift slightly upwards in Fig. 3 if compared to the trends deeper in the core.

These findings provide valuable insights into the depth-dependent effect of LSP on residual stresses in both as-printed and machined configurations. Understanding these trends is crucial for optimising LSP parameters and their subsequent impact on the mechanical behaviour of treated components.

B) Fatigue life analysis

Two testing facilities, namely CTU in Prague and OTH Amberg-Weiden, cooperated in described fatigue experiments. To ensure uniformity and consistency in testing, the specimens were divided between these facilities, with each group subjected to similar testing equipment.

During the fatigue experiments, two distinct testing frequencies were employed, with CTU using 120 Hz and OTH operating at 90 Hz. This difference is deemed minor in relation to the potential frequency effect on fatigue life. The experiments were designed to stop at any of these specific conditions if reached:

- A drop in testing frequency by 10 Hz.
- A change in load amplitude by ± 0.5 kN.
- Alteration in static loads by ± 0.5 kN.
- If 10^7 cycles were reached, the test was designated as a run-out. The specimen was subsequently subjected to higher load amplitude and new test was run. The target new amplitude was increased to at least twice the previous stress amplitude.

Fig. 4 clearly illustrates the beneficial impact of LSP procedure on the fatigue performance of specimens. The series NoLSP(A) where it was not applied at all displays the lowest performance. A noticeable difference is observed when comparing LSP1 and LSP2 configurations for the as-printed series. Notably, LSP2 exhibits a more positive influence on fatigue strength compared to LSP1 parameters.

Regarding the machined specimens, the fatigue strength of LSP1 and LSP2 configurations appears to be nearly identical, which conforms to the residual stress profiles in Fig. 3. However, it seems that LSP2 still provides a slight advantage for the machined series, though the differences are not so pronounced as observed in the as-built series.

Notably, the blank points in Fig. 4 indicate the specimens that did not fail in the critical cross-section. If these were not classical run-outs (at 10 million cycles), the failures in such cases occurred near or within the machined thread used for fixing the specimen in the testing machine. This observation suggests that the LSP treatment was powerful enough to transfer the critical cross-section of some specimens from the central part with the highest amplitude of stress to the grip area. This phenomenon may be attributed to the applying LSP solely on the hourglass surface, while the region around the machined head, where the thread was cut, did not undergo LSP treatment. Consequently, the residual stresses induced by the machining process may have contributed to the redistribution of stresses around the machined head region. Due to this issue, the transition to the fatigue limit domain for machined specimens is not clearly visible.

The regression by Kohout-Věchet formula describes usually well the transition to fatigue limit domain and to the quasi-static domain [16], but the fatigue curves of machined configurations (LSP1(M) and LSP2(M)) has no clear bend into the fatigue limit region. Due to the premature breaks at threaded grips, the as-built configurations seem to achieve higher fatigue strengths.

Overall, these findings indicate the significant influence of LSP on fatigue strength, particularly for the as-built series, where LSP2 showcases superior performance compared to LSP1. Moreover, the

observed effects on the machined series suggest that LSP can further enhance the fatigue strength, although the mechanism of stress redistribution around the machined head calls for further investigation.

FIGURE 4 Fatigue curves of five different configurations with the same heat treatment but different surface treatment: NoLSP(A) as a reference fatigue curve, LSP1(A), LSP2(A), LSP1(M) and LSP2(M).

FIGURE 5 (a) Fracture surface of the NoLSP(A) specimen with the cracks leading from the specimen surface shown, where orange shows the main crack on the specimen's surface ;(b) Fracture surface of the LSP2(A) specimen with the shown crack leading from the defect from the centre (red arrow pointing at lack of fusion).

Fracture surface analysis revealed a notable impact of Laser Shock Peening (LSP). Despite the presence of numerous defects on the surfaces of printed samples, LSP exhibited the capability to mitigate surface notches, yielding significant results. It is noteworthy that all specimens subjected to

LSP displayed a central crack pattern. For instance, Fig. 5 provides a clear illustration, showcasing a typical specimen from the NoLSP(A) series on the left, and an LSP2(A) specimen on the right, where a crack originates from an internal defect. This prevalent pattern of crack initiation from internal defects was consistently observed across fracture surfaces in series treated with LSP.

C) Surface temperature monitoring

In this study, the thermal response of cyclically loaded specimens was investigated by measuring the temperature evolution on the specimen's surface using infrared thermal cameras (Flir A315 at CTU in Prague with NETD = 50mK and Fluke RSE600 at OTH Amberg-Weiden with NETD = 40mK). The surface of a specimen was coated with a black paint with measured emissivity. The research findings are summarised below. The primary references for our research are the works by Torabian et al. [17] and Meneghetti [18]. The heat equation used in our research represents the core of our focused problem:

$$\rho c \dot{\Theta} - \rho c \frac{\Theta}{\tau} = S_t + d_1 ; \Theta = T_{loaded} - T_{ref} \quad (1)$$

In this study, the temperature difference (Θ) is measured between the loaded specimen (T_{loaded}) and a reference non-loaded specimen (T_{ref}), which is placed adjacent to the examined loaded specimen, as shown in Fig. 2a. The reference specimen acts as a temperature sensor for the ambient temperature, effectively compensating for fluctuations in the surroundings of both specimens and minimising potential temperature sensor drift.

The heat equation used to analyse the thermal response of the cyclically loaded specimen consists of two terms on the left side. The first term represents the inner energy based on the derivative of the stabilised temperature. The second term, denoted by a specific time constant (τ), characterises heat conduction and relates to the time required for the surface temperature of the loaded specimen (loading of which has been stopped) to cool down to either the ambient temperature or the temperature of the reference specimen.

Furthermore, the equation includes two additional terms. One term represents the energy associated with the thermoelastic effect, while the other term (dissipation) takes into account the hysteresis of plastic deformation [17].

In practical measurements, the equation is integrated over time because the infrared thermal camera used has a frame rate lower than the load frequency imposed by the testing equipment. Consequently, the thermoelastic effect can be disregarded in the analysis.

In our case, we are using the stabilised temperature to characterise the material response to cyclic loading, so the time dependent first term is equal to zero. Then we can simplify Eq. (1) to:

$$\rho c \frac{\Theta}{\tau} = -d_1 ; \Theta = d_1 \cdot \left(-\rho c \frac{\Theta}{\tau} \right)^{-1} \quad (2)$$

The integration of variables over time is denoted by wave marks above the respective symbols. The temperature evolution during cyclic loading typically exhibits three distinct phases, as depicted in Fig. 6 (a). The first phase is characterised by the initial incline R_0 , which usually lasts between 5,000 to 7,000 cycles for this specific material and specimen design. The second phase is marked by a

stabilised temperature difference. Finally, the third phase, characterised by the inclination R_y , represents a rapid transition leading to specimen failure.

To further investigate the stabilised temperature behaviour in the second phase, a step self-heating (S-H) test was conducted to monitor the stabilised temperature response under various subsequently increasing load amplitudes. This test was designed to observe the temperature response to stress values ranging from below the fatigue limit up to stress amplitudes corresponding to the low-cycle fatigue (LCF) region.

The S-H experiment was focused on defining the number of cycles required to reach stabilised temperatures at specific stress amplitudes. Subsequently, the test block length was determined based on tests with a single load amplitude, which served to establish S-N curves. The findings indicate that the transition to Phase 2, characterised by stabilised temperatures, typically occurs around 5,000 to 6,000 cycles under our testing conditions. Accordingly, the load block duration was set to 7,000 cycles. For higher load amplitudes, the transition to Phase 2 occurs earlier. Therefore, testing blocks with amplitudes exceeding 100 MPa were examined with a block length of 5,000 cycles and over 120MPa with a block length of 3,500 cycles. Figure 6 (b) does not show us any differences between tested configurations, although it could be mentioned that the thermal response was slightly higher for machined specimens, but no further analysis was performed in this paper. The observed knee point of expected bilinear evolution [9; 7; 19; 14] is visible around the stress amplitude of 70MPa.

FIGURE 6 (a) The temperature evolution during constant-amplitude cyclic loading leading to failure (at N_f) can be divided into three distinct phases. The area with grey background is equal to the limiting energy F . (b) The Self-Heating step tests result in four different cases representing each of the five different configurations.

CONCLUSION

In this research study, the significant effect of Laser Shock Peening (LSP) on the residual stresses within specimens was investigated. Extensive measurements were conducted to assess the induced residual stresses at various depths below the surface. The results demonstrated that LSP induced compressive residual stresses, enhancing the material's resistance to fatigue and mechanical degradation. The impact of LSP on residual stresses primarily affected the near-surface region, particularly in the initial layers of the as-printed specimens. For machined specimens, the differences between LSP1 and LSP2 configurations were still evident, with LSP2 providing a slight advantage in axial residual stresses.

In the fatigue experiments, LSP showed a beneficial impact on fatigue performance, with LSP2 exhibiting superior performance compared to LSP1 in the as-printed series. For the machined series, both LSP1 and LSP2 configurations demonstrated nearly identical fatigue strength, but LSP2 still showed a slight advantage. The LSP treatment was potent enough to transfer the critical cross-section

of some specimens away from the central part with the highest stress amplitude, leading to failure near or within the machined thread region.

The final section of the paper was focused on investigating the thermal response of cyclically loaded specimens using infrared thermal cameras. The temperature evolution during cyclic loading was divided into three phases, and a step self-heating test was conducted to observe the stabilised temperature response under various load amplitudes. The findings indicated that the transition to the phase of stabilised temperatures occurred around 5,000 to 7,000 cycles under the testing conditions depending on the amplitude of load.

Overall, this research provides valuable insights into the depth-dependent effect of LSP on residual stresses and its significant influence on fatigue strength. The results highlight the importance of understanding these trends for optimising LSP parameters and improving the material's mechanical behaviour. The research also introduces a method for monitoring the thermal response of cyclically loaded specimens, which can aid in further understanding material behaviour under different stress levels.

In conclusion, the study emphasises the potential of Laser Shock Peening in enhancing the mechanical properties and fatigue performance of components manufactured through additive manufacturing processes. The findings have implications for industries that rely on metal 3D printing, as they can utilise LSP as a post-processing technique to improve the fatigue resistance and overall reliability of their products. Additionally, the research provides a foundation for future studies in the field of thermal response monitoring during cyclic loading, contributing to a better understanding of material behaviour under various stress conditions.

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